

Studies on Quaternary β -Ketoalkyl Iodides and Triiodides of some Heterocyclic Bases

J. P. SAXENA*, VANDANA LODHA and PRITI KHIVSARA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

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Isobutyl methyl ketone reacted with iodine in presence of heterocyclic tertiary bases, viz. pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, and α -, β - and γ -picolines using isopropanol as solvent, resulting in the formation of a series of quaternary *N*-(2-oxopentyl-4-methyl)ammonium iodides. When acetic acid was used as medium of reaction the triiodides of quaternary *N*-(2-oxopentyl-4-methyl)ammonium iodides were isolated. On using excess of heterocyclic tertiary base in the reaction, no triiodide formation took place. The quaternary compounds responded to the characteristic enol betaine test. These compounds showed antibacterial activity at 100 ppm against human pathogen, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

IN an attempt to synthesise the quaternary β -ketoalkyl derivatives of heterocyclic tertiary bases with aliphatic methyl ketones and iodine, the effect of different solvents, acid catalysis and temperature on the reaction has been studied. A perusal of literature shows that some of the quaternary iodides and triiodides have even been tried for their antibacterial activity. In the present investigation we report the synthesis of a new series of quaternary β -ketoalkyl-ammonium iodides of some new heterocyclic tertiary bases hitherto unreported, by making use of isopropanol as solvent. The effect of appropriate solvent shows a bearing on the yield of β -ketoalkyl salts and the use of isopropanol seems to facilitate the formation of the products.

A number of quaternary β -ketoalkyl iodides have been synthesised¹⁻⁴ and later extended⁵ to aliphatic methylketones using methanol as a solvent. In the present investigation by carrying out this reaction in isopropanol as medium, it was possible to isolate the quaternary β -ketoalkyl iodides using isobutyl methyl ketone, and pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline and α -, β - and γ -picolines, respectively. The products were characterised by their elemental analysis, uv and ir spectral data. They showed characteristic colour reactions with dilute alkali, picryl chloride and chloranil. On carrying out this reaction in acetic acid medium, the quaternary β -ketoalkylammonium iodides (1) and their respective triiodides (3) were formed.

where, $\text{N} \langle \rangle$ is pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, and α -, β - and γ -picolines. When the excess of the base was used, the triiodides formed in very low yields. They were separated from each other by making use of their solubility characteristics. The triiodides dissolved in acetone and could be recrystallised from absolute ethanol. All the triiodides showed I_3^- characteristics absorption at 290 nm and 360 nm. Both 1 and 3 gave intensely coloured betaines with 0.1 N $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{NaOH}$ which could be extracted with chloroform to give yellow coloured betaines.

Betaine IV gave different characteristic colour reactions with picryl chloride (deep red) and chloranil (violet).

The physical and analytical data of the compounds are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Antibacterial activity: Antibacterial activity of the compounds was carried out against a human

TABLE 1—QUATERNARY *N*-(2-OXOPENTYL-4-METHYL)AMMONIUM IODIDE (1)

Sl. no.	Base	Molecular formula	M.p.* °C	Yield %	Physical state (crystals)	$\lambda_{\max}$ O=O cm^{-1}	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
							N	I
1.	Pyridinium	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}$	190	65	Light yellow	1665	4.49 (4.59)	41.39 (41.68)
2.	Quinolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}$	198	68	Yellowish brown	1680	3.87 (3.94)	35.65 (35.77)
3.	Isoquinolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}$	194	64	Light yellow	1660	3.90 (3.94)	35.70 (35.77)
4.	α -Picolinium**	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}$	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.	β -Picolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}$	180	61	Brown-red	1635	4.32 (4.38)	39.70 (39.80)
6.	γ -Picolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}$	180	62	Brown-red	1640	4.30 (4.38)	39.75 (39.8)

* Determined on a Kofler instrument and uncorrected.

** Isolated as picrate, m.p. 130°.

TABLE 2—QUATERNARY *N*-(2-OXOPENTYL-4-METHYL)AMMONIUM TRIIODIDES (3)

Sl. no.	Base	Molecular formula	M.p.* °C	Yield %	Physical state (needles)	$\lambda_{\max}$ O=O cm^{-1}	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
							N	I
1.	Pyridinium	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}_3$	208	69	Brown-black	1670	4.49 (4.59)	41.39 (41.68)
2.	Quinolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}_3$	200	67	Brown-green	1682	3.87 (3.94)	35.65 (35.71)
3.	Isoquinolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}_3$	204	65	Brown-green	1669	3.90 (3.94)	35.70 (35.77)
4.	α -Picolinium**	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}_3$	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.	β -Picolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}_3$	225	63	Brown-black	1640	4.32 (4.38)	39.70 (39.80)
6.	γ -Picolinium	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NOI}_3$	240	67	Brown-black	1646	4.30 (4.38)	39.75 (39.80)

* Determined on a Kofler instrument and uncorrected.

** Isolated as picrate, m.p. 130°.

pathogenic bacterium, *Staphylococcus aureus* by utilizing petri dish zonal inhibition technique. Graded concentrations of each compound (10-500 ppm) were prepared in sterile water. Filter paper discs immersed in each concentration, were placed on the surface of nutrient agar in petri dish, previously inoculated with *S. aureus*. Ten discs were used for each concentration. Presence of inhibition zone was observed after 3 days of incubation at 25°.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds showed antibacterial activity at 100 ppm concentration, however, the inhibition zone at lower concentrations (50 ppm) could be observed only in the case of *N*-(2-oxopentyl-4-methyl)-quinolinium iodide (2).

Experimental

Quaternary β -ketoalkylammonium iodides (1) : Iodine (12.7 g) was dissolved in 0.1 mole of heterocyclic tertiary base (0.1 mol). To this isobutyl methyl ketone (0.1 mol, 10 ml) was added and then diluted with isopropanol (25 ml). The reaction

mixture was heated under reflux on hot-plate for 4-5 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and cooled overnight. The crystals of hydroiodide of the base (2) and quaternary β -ketoalkylammonium iodide (1) separated. The separation of 1 was effected by fractional crystallisation and recrystallisation from isopropanol. The product was dried and gave single spot on tlc using methanol-ethylacetate (1 : 9).

Quaternary β -ketoalkylammonium triiodides (3) : Iodine (6.0 g) was dissolved in 0.1 mole of heterocyclic base (0.1 mol). To this isobutyl methyl ketone (0.1 mol) was added and then diluted with glacial acetic acid (50 ml). The red brown diiodide of the base turned black immediately. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux on water-bath for 2-3 h and left overnight. The crystals of 1, 2 and 3 were obtained. The separation of 2 was made by absolute ethanol and 3 was separated by using acetone as solvent in which it dissolved. When the amount of the base was increased in the original reaction mixture no triiodide was obtained.

In an alternative method, the solution of 1 (0.1 M) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was treated with iodine (1.27 g, 0.01 mol). On cooling, shining

black-brown crystals of **3** separated which were treated with acetone so that the unreacted **1** remained undissolved and **3** went into solution. **3** was recovered from the acetone extract on evaporation and then recrystallised twice from absolute ethanol.

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